

Local Government in India

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Asha Sarangi and Lipika Ravichandran

Centre for Political Studies
Jawaharlal Nehru University

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Jawaharlal Nehru University: Asha Sarangi, Lipika Ravichandran
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Delhi Confused me/Pixabay

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in India	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in India: An Introduction	7
2.2. <i>School, Educational Services and their Delivery Mechanisms</i>	10
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in India: An Introduction.....	15
3.2. <i>Fiscal Autonomy: Restraints and Limits</i>	18
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in India: An Introduction	23
4.2. <i>Decentralization and Democratic Governance</i>	27
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in India: An Introduction.....	31
5.2. <i>Local Governments and their Functioning</i>	33
6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in India: An Introduction	40
6.2. <i>Sanitation Development</i>	43

Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in India: An Introduction

Asha Sarangi and Lipika Ravichandran, *Centre for Political Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University*

In India, local financial arrangements at the level of local self-governments are a complicated system as there are institutional differences at urban and rural levels. Local authorities in India are responsible for state owned projects, wherein they use their resources for the operation of these projects. It is an important imperative on the part of the local governments for the development of municipal bodies and districts. In the domain of financial functionality, rural and local governments have a similarity in the pattern of expenditures for civic and social services, however the degree of expenditure varies. The varied expenditure depends on the revenue generation and the needs of the rural and urban population. The urban local bodies have more revenue sources and they collect more taxes as they have a larger population to take into consideration. Whereas the rural local bodies have less revenue due to smaller population. But the services provided by both the bodies are almost similar but different in scale. For example, the urban local body caters till tertiary health care whereas the rural local body provides only primary health care. The estimate for expenditure is included in the five-year plans which show both planned and unplanned expenditures for each state and its local population. For example, during the 2016-17 cycle, in Tamil Nadu, the urban local bodies spent Rs. 13,301 crores (approximately €2 billion), while *Panchayat Raj* Institutions spent Rs. 4,960 crores (approximately €0.7 billion).⁹

Based on the study by the Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER) in March 2019, prepared for the Fifteenth Finance Commission, urbanization in India has occurred at a rapid rate. The urban and rural local governments have the weakest financial autonomy which adversely affects their ability to perform core functions and deliver services. Moreover, they lack behind in providing any stimulus to economic growth.

According to the 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act (Rural Local Bodies) and the 74th Constitutional Amendment Act (Urban Local Bodies) the state legislature has the following powers in order to strengthen the finance of the rural and urban local government:

- authorize a *panchayat*/municipality to levy, collect and appropriate taxes, duties, tolls and fees;
- assign to a *panchayat*/municipality taxes, duties, tolls and fees levied and collected by the state government;

⁹ Kumarapalayam R Shanmugam, 'Tamil Nadu State Government Finances' (Madras School of Economics 2018) <https://fincomindia.nic.in/writereaddata/html_en_files/fincom15/StudyReports/24.pdf>.

- provide for making grants in aid to the *panchayats*/municipality from the consolidated fund of the state.

The act also provides to constitute a finance commission to review the financial position of the local governments.

The resources of the local bodies can be categorized into three categories:

- own resources;
- shared/assigned resources;
- grants and aids.

In rural local bodies, their own resources are generated in the forms of house tax, cattle tax, commercial crop tax, etc., whereas in urban local bodies, their own resources are generated in the forms of property tax, profession tax, etc.

According to the Economic Survey of 2017 - 18, *panchayats* received 95 per cent of its revenue from external sources and only 5 per cent were generated on their own. This is because of tax evasion and at the same time states have not devolved the taxation powers to the local bodies. To conclude, the local bodies are heavily dependent on external sources such as the state and the center for its resources in turn exposing them to high risks.

The ICRIER report states that, 'municipal revenues/expenditures in India have been stagnating at around 1 per cent of the GDP for over a decade.'¹⁰ The report further states that finance and expenditure have been a reason of contestation as the constitutional provisions on the devolution of power has been feeble and there are administrative failures in its implementation.

India follows a pattern of decentralization where the central and state governments have the sole discretionary powers to disburse financial arrangements to urban and local governments. Based on rapid urbanization, abysmal poverty conditions, and farmers suicide in present day India, it is important that fiscal autonomy be implemented at the level of local governments. Fiscal autonomy means independence in generation and utilization of fiscal resources. Example-levy and collection of taxes and fees on their own by Urban Local Bodies.

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Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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